

Prevention Practices to Address Common Crimes Committed

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Abstract:- This is a case study determined prevention practices employed to address the most common crimes committed in selected barangays in the Philippines. Data gathered through interview were collated and analyzed. The findings of the study revealed that prevention practices were as follows; warning or reprimand, payment of damages, no issuance of barangay clearance to a none registered voter, installation of Close Circuit Televisions (CCTV) and mediation. It is then concluded that prevention practices employed vary on crimes committed.

I. INTRODUCTION

The first settlers in the Philippines were believed to have arrived here thousand years before Christ. These settlers were nomads. Nomads were those who wandered from one place to another in search for food.

These nomads soon realized that there was a need for them to group themselves and settle in one place for them to help one another in raising animals and planting vegetables. When grouped together, however, problems were encountered when members of the community committed some infractions against the others. They realized that there was a need for them to organize a body to arrest offenders and conduct trials. Hence, trial by ordeal and like were practiced to determine whether a person was guilty or not of a charge (Timpac, 2013).

He added that when Magellan found that there were already organized settlers being governed by local Chieftains, like Sultans and Rajahs. Each Sultan or Rajah headed a Barangay, whose duty is to conduct trial and punish those who were found guilty.

Eduardo (2014) portrayed that geographically speaking, the Philippines is in the tropic zone and theoretically, Filipinos are hot-blooded with very volatile temperament. Summer and rainy seasons showed no difference in crime rates as they are almost of the same level irrespective of the locality. Further, criminal behavior of the people is greatly affected by poor economic and social conditions.

Authorities in the field of law enforcement and public safety have proved that the following are the principal causes of juvenile and adult's anti-social behavior: hatred, personal gain, revenge, passion, insanity and unpopular laws (Eduardo, 2014).

He added that there were common sociological causes of crimes in the country such as; lack of parental guidance, broken home and family, lack of recreational facilities, lack of employment, school failure, misdirected religious teachings, mass communication media and political causes.

The NSW Bureau of Crime Statistics and Research reiterated that there is no single factor or set of factors which causes an individual to become involved in crime. Being criminal is not like having a disease. (NSW Bureau of Crime Statistics and Research, 2001).

Crime is present in various forms in the country, and remains a serious issue throughout the country. Baguio City has been named among the safest city in Southeast Asia 2018 according to a newly released data from Numbeo. Baguio City has been ranked the 6th place with a record of 59.43 safety index (wowcordillera, 2018)

II. METHODOLOGY

This is a case study determining the crime prevention and intervention practices employed to address crimes committed in two barangays in Baguio City (Barangay 1) and Cabanatuan City (Barangay 2), Philippines. The respondents were 2 barangay secretaries. Data were gathered through informal interview and observation. The gathered data were recorded, rank, collated, analyzed and interpreted.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This area presents the most common committed crimes and the prevention practices implemented by the 2 barangays to address the crimes committed.

➤ *Most common committed crimes*

Table 1 presents the most committed crimes in barangay 1 (Baguio City).

Table 1 Most common committed crimes in Barangay 1 Baguio City

Cases	Rank	No. of Cases
Malicious Mischief	1	4
Collection of Sum of Money	2	3
Physical Injury	3	1
TOTAL		8

As shown in the above table, the highest which rank number 1 is malicious mischief with a number 4 cases. Accordingly, this happens after a drinking session among neighbors. It is a habit of some of the residents of Baguio City to have a drinking session after a day of laborious hard work. As the barangay secretary 1 quoted “Agwala wala dan no nabartek da” (intoxicated by liquor they start to create nuisance).

It simply implies that malicious mischief cases were caused by alcohol, it doesn't mean that all residents of the said barangay are alcoholic. It's just that, it is a practice where males (young adult and adults) relax after a day of labor especially during pay day.

The result of the study reveals that malicious mischief as a result of alcohol is somewhat related to Neutralizing Definition theory where a person justifies committing a crime by making it seem that although the act itself might be wrong, under certain conditions it is all right. That the offenders portray to defend themselves as under the influence of liquor during the commission of the crime to neutralize their wrong action. (Neutralization Theory in Criminology: Definition & Challenges, 2016)

The result of the study give with Life Course Theory where this theory focuses directly on the connection between individual lives and the historical and socioeconomic context in which these lives unfold. Malicious Mischief was committed due to the practice or event that has been done overtime, it is what they observed and soon will be their actions. (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Health Resources and Services Administration, Maternal and Child Health Bureau, 2010)

The second most common committed crime on the same barangay is the collection of sums of money. From the 3 cases, 2 of which were renters or borders. The complainants are usually the Indians (Bombay) because of their loansharking business (5'6). When the borrower received the loan, they will disappear from the barangay. Since they are renters/borders, their whereabouts are undetermined.

The least common crime committed on the same barangay is physical injury. According to the secretary, that 1 case of physical injury was the result of a heated argument between young adults after a drinking session in a birthday

party. The secretary narrated “Idi nabartek, Agkulkulit, isu dinanog dan a” (they become stubborn when intoxicated, that escalated to a fist fight).

Table 2 Most common committed crimes in Barangay 2 (Cabanatuan City)

Cases	Rank	No. of Cases
Estafa	1	3
Theft	2	2
Slight Physical Injury	3	2
Total		7

Table 2 presents the most common crimes committed in barangay 2 (Cabanatuan City). As the barangay secretary said the main cause of misunderstanding between neighbors is loaning of money, as she narrates “Madami kasing Nag oofer sa kanila na lending, kaya na ceengaganyo sila mag utang” (There are so many who offer them lending, so that they can be enticed to borrow).

The second most committed crime in the same barangay is theft. The barangay is located near a university where there are 5000 population of enrolled students. Because of that boarding houses grow like mushroom in the barangay. Most of the victims were students but the alleged suspects were not residents of the barangay.

The result of the study is somewhat connected with the Routine Activity Theory. Where the thieves study the routine activities of their possible targets which were students. Students more often than not are negligent and unconscious of their actions, they adhere to their daily routine without their knowledge that they were already exposing themselves to danger. (State of New South Wales through the Department of Attorney General and Justice, 2011)

The least common crime committed is slight physical injury, barangay 2 is a small barangay and has lesser population, the permanent residents almost know each other and most of the renters are all students of the nearby university.

Above all, the result of the study implies that the residents of the two barangays (Baguio City and Cabanatuan City) were law abiding citizens. The small number of reported crimes as well as the less serious degree of crimes committed is a proof that the barangay has an effective preventive measure to maintain their peace and order.

➤ *Prevention Practices employed to address most common crimes committed*

Each barangay has their own strategy in dealing with their most common crimes committed, since they differ in most common crimes committed, they have different prevention practices.

➤ *Barangay 1, Prevention Practices*

Barangay 1 employed the following prevention practices: for the cases of malicious mischief, the barangay warned or reprimand the offender and required to pay the damages incurred if there is.

For the cases on collection of money, some of the offenders were renters and their whereabouts cannot be determined, the loan shark commonly referred to as 5'6 refers the case to the barangay for records purposes. But if the offender is present, the barangay invites both parties (the offender and the loan shark) for mediation. Upon determination of facts, the barangay verbally reprimands or warn the loaner and required to pay the amount of money loaned. Once repeated, the penalty is expulsion from the barangay.

For the case of physical injury, the prevention practices employed is somewhat the same with the two previous cases; warning and payment of damages if any. The only difference is that the offender was asked to sign a promissory note indicating not to commit the same in front of the barangay chairman, the police officers from the nearest police station (if reported to the police) who has jurisdiction over the said barangay and the Barangay Peace Keeping Action Team (BPAT).

The study finds that prevention practices employed by this barangay is processed; majority cases brought before the attention of the barangay was amicably settled. According to the secretary, there were cases brought directly to Police Station but were referred back to the barangay level for mediation.

The study implies that the actions employed by the barangay is effective because of the small number of reported crimes.

➤ *Barangay 2, Prevention Practices*

Barangay 2 employed the following prevention practices to address the most common crimes committed; Since, the top 1 most common committed crime was Estafa, the barangay strictly implements the no issuance of barangay clearance which is the primary requirement for lending companies to a none registered voter of the said barangay. The barangay secretary pointed out that even if they are a registered voter and a permanent resident of the barangay if they have already a record of not paying the loaned money, they will not also be given barangay clearance.

For the second top most common crime committed which was theft. The barangay installed Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) on hot spot areas or crucial areas to monitor the movement of the residents and visitors of the barangay. As to my observation they have installed 8 cameras in strategic locations.

For cases of slight physical injury which was the third most common crime committed, the barangay employed mediation to settle the dispute.

The study showed that barangay 2 has a solid and concrete prevention practices to address the most common committed crimes.

➤ *Barangay 1 VS. Barangay 2*

The most common crimes committed in the 2 barangays were almost alike except for malicious mischief for barangay 1 and theft for barangay 2.

In barangay 1, the most rampant crime is malicious mischief as a result of alcohol. Their culture of having a drinking session after a day of work is one factor or reason for the commission of such. While theft is the most rampant for barangay 2, this is because of the numerous possible victims which are the students in boarding houses facing the university.

The study implies that both barangays devise their own prevention program according to their own circumstances. Barangay 1 employs soft programs like warning, paying of damages and promissory note to solve the crimes committed while barangay 2 has a more solid and concrete programs like non issuance of barangay clearance for loan purposes if they are not a registered voter to control the crime of estafa. For their theft cases, the barangay installed CCTV to monitor and record suspicious activities. Lastly, they have the mediation program for slight physical injury cases.

The study also shows that they design prevention programs that fits their purpose which was to maintain the harmonious relationship among their residents as well as the peace and order of the barangay.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: the most common crimes committed in both barangays were minor offenses. Most common crimes committed differs in every barangay this is due to the fact that they have different cultures and different situations. Prevention practices employed vary in every barangay. They devise prevention programs that fits their needs.

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